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Review Article

**A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON ORAL IN-SITU GEL FOR
PERIODONTAL DISEASE****Puri G. Ashutosh^{*1}, Atram C. Dr. Sandeep², Mandwe S. Vrushabh³, Bhonde G. Akash⁴,
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Abstract:

The current review on in situ gelling systems becomes one of the most popular and prominent. In-situ forming polymeric gelling systems has become prominent among novel drug delivery system (NDDS) in recent years due to advantages such as sustained and prolonged drug action, improved patient compliance and reduced frequency of administration of the drug in comparison to conventional drug delivery system (DDS). This is a type of mucoadhesive DDS where the polymeric formulation is in sol form before administration and once comes in contact with body fluids; it undergoes gelation to form a gel. The formulation of gel depends upon factors like temperature modulation, pH changes, presence of ions and ultraviolet irradiation from which drug gets released in sustained and controlled manner. Conventional formulation for the treatment of dental diseases has certain drawbacks. A new concept of in situ gel was developed to overcome the shortcoming of conventional formulation which deals with dental diseases. Conventional oral formulations like solution, suspension, and ointments have many disadvantages which result into poor bioavailability of drug in the buccal cavity. In-situ forming polymeric formulation drug delivery systems is in sol form before administration in the body, but once administered, undergoes gelation in-situ to form a gel. There are several possible mechanisms that lead to in situ gel formation: solvent exchange, UV-irradiation, ionic cross-linkage, pH change, and temperature modulation. The article provides insight on natural polymers as well as synthetic polymers, including systems based on thermally triggered system, pH triggered system, ionic cross linking method, enzymatic cross linking method etc. Lastly, this review summarizes about the characterization of oral in situ gels including different evaluation such as drug content study, pH & viscosity determination, texture analysis, spreadability, gel strength, gelling time, sterility testing, in-vitro drug release study, stability study etc.

Key words: In-situ Dental Gel, Periodontal diseases, Polymers, Periodontitis

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Gel is the state which exists between solid and liquid phase. The solid component comprises a three dimensional network of inter-linked molecules which immobilizes the liquid phase.^[1] In situ gelation is a process of gel formation at the site of action after the formulation has been applied at the site. In situ gel phenomenon based upon liquid solution of drug formulation and converted into semi-solid mucoadhesive key depot.^[2] In situ gel forming formulations are currently a novel idea of delivering drugs to patients as a liquid dosage form, yet achieve sustained release of drug for the desired period. Different delivery systems based on polymers have been developed, which are able to increase the residence time of the formulation at absorption site of drugs.^[3] Also its mucoadhesive property prevent it from getting washed by salivary fluid inside the buccal cavity. In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in water soluble polymers that are able to form gels after application to delivery site. These so called in situ gelling polymers are highly advantageous compared with other polymers because, in contrast to very strong gels, they can be easily applied in liquid form to the site of drug absorption. At the site of drug absorption, they swell to form a strong gel that is capable of prolonging the residence time of the active substance. Hydrogels are the polymeric materials with three dimensional networks, which have gained much attention in biomedical fields as carriers for drugs, protein, cells, and others because of their good biocompatibility, solute permeability and tunable release characteristics.^[4] The retaining ability of a large amount of water within their structures which results in high water content and soft-surface properties is the character that makes them compromised on the surrounding tissues and leads to a good biocompatibility. Because of the present busy life system even in common man dental diseases are most widespread chronic disorders.^[5-7] Periodontal disease refers to a group of problems that arise in the sulcus, the crevice between the gum and tooth the common causative organisms includes Actinobacillus, actinomycetemcomitans as a pathogen responsible for juvenile periodontitis, staphylococci subspecies epidermidis and aureus are responsible adult periodontal disease.^[8] Site-specific therapy for periodontitis has three potential advantages, it decreased drug doses, increased drug concentration at the site of infection and reduced systemic side effects such as gastrointestinal distress.^[9] Periodontal diseases treatment with a localized drug delivery system aims at delivering therapeutic agent at sufficient level inside the periodontal pocket and at the same time minimizing the side effects associated with systemic

drug administration. Thus it increases patient's compliance.^[10]

1.1 Dental disease

Periodontal Disease: The word "Perio" means around, and "dental" refers to teeth. Teeth and their supporting (periodontal) structures are of main importance to oral health. Dental diseases are among the widest spread chronic disorder affecting mankind.^[11] Periodontal disease are a group of clinical conditions which affect the supportive structure of the teeth and are characterized by infection and inflammation. The development of periodontitis involves periodontal tissue breakdown and result from an interaction between the affecting organisms. Conventional therapy, based on scaling, surgery and the use of antibiotics or antimicrobials has been proposed.^[12]

These conditions are characterized by a destruction of the periodontal ligament, a resorption of the alveolar bone and the migration of the junctional epithelium along the tooth surface. The clinical signs of periodontitis are changes in the morphology of gingival tissues, bleeding upon probing as well as periodontal pocket formation. This pocket provides an ideal environment for the growth and proliferation of anaerobic pathogenic bacteria.^[13]

1.2 Classification of Periodontal Disease:

The American Academy of Periodontology classification system identifies distinct types of periodontal diseases, clinical appearance, rate of disease progression, pathogenic microbial flora and systemic influences. The two major categories are Gingivitis and Periodontitis.

1.2.1 Gingivitis:

Gingivitis is a chronic inflammatory process limited to the gingiva without either attachment loss or alveolar bone loss. It is one of the most frequent oral diseases, affecting more than 90% of the population, regardless of age, sex, or race.^[14] Gingivitis can usually be treated simply. Gingivitis is often caused by inadequate oral hygiene. Plaque and tartar are removed from teeth; the inflamed tissues around a tooth usually heal quickly and completely.^[15]

Types of gingivitis

a) Plaque-Associated Gingivitis :- Gingival redness, edema, bleeding upon probing, enlargement and tenderness

b) Chronic Gingivitis :- Inflammation of the gingival, resulting in loss of clinical attachment due to periodontal ligament destruction and loss of the adjacent supporting bone

c) Acute Necrotizing Ulcerative Gingivitis :- Patients diagnosed with Acute Necrotizing Ulcerative Gingivitis may present with the following clinical findings: Papillary necrosis, bleeding, pain and fetor oris (odor).

d) Gingivitis Associated with Systemic Conditions or Medications :-

- **Hormone-Induced Gingival Inflammation:** - Gingival redness, bleeding upon probing, edema and gingival enlargement associated with proliferation of blood vessels.
- **Drug-Influenced Gingivitis :-** Fibrotic gingival response, pseudo pockets and bleeding upon probing.
- **Linear Gingival Erythema (LGE) :-** Patients that are HIV+ may exhibit this type of gingival response.

e) Gingival Manifestations of Systemic Diseases and Mucocutaneous Lesions :-

- **Bacterial, Viral or Fungal:-** Two examples Acute Herpetic Gingivostomatitis or Candida Albicans.
- **Blood Dyscrasias (for example Acute Monocytic Leukemia):-** Clinical Findings: spontaneous bleeding upon probing or by simply touching the gingival tissues.
- **Mucocutaneous Diseases (Lichen Planus, Cicatricial Pemphigoid):-** include; Lichen Planus, Pemphigus Vulgaris and Desquamative Gingivitis.^[16]

1.2.2 Periodontitis

Periodontitis is the common oral disease affecting many people around the world. It is defined as an inflammation and progressive destruction of the tooth supporting structures (periodontium). Periodontitis involves progressive loss of the alveolar bone around the teeth, and if left untreated, can lead to the loosening and subsequent loss of teeth. A diagnosis of Periodontitis is established by inspecting the soft gum tissues around the teeth with a probe (i.e. a clinical exam) and by evaluating the patient's x-ray films (i.e.

a radiographic exam), to determine the amount of bone loss around the teeth. This disease results from interaction between specific host defence mechanisms and dental plaque bio films that colonize on the tooth surfaces at or below the gingival margin.^[16,17]

Types of periodontitis:-

a) Plaque-Associated Periodontitis:- The presence of local factors such as plaque is usually comparable with the disease progression.

b) Early-Onset Periodontitis:-

- ❖ **Prepubertal:** A rare periodontal disease, onset is often during or immediately following eruption of the deciduous dentition and rapid destruction of bone.
- ❖ **Juvenile Periodontitis:** In these patients, there is rapid loss of attachment, bilateral symmetry is common, destruction of bone is often localized to first permanent molars, and mild to moderate inflammatory response.
- ❖ **Rapidly Progressive:** This case is a young female diagnosed with Rapidly Progressive Periodontitis.

c) Periodontitis Associated with Systemic Diseases:-

With certain systemic conditions the inflammatory response is altered in the presence of local irritants thereby, accelerating the progression of periodontal disease.

d) Necrotizing Ulcerative Periodontitis:- Findings may include erythema, ulceration and necrosis of the gingival margin, with destruction of the supporting bone.

e) Refractory:- These types of cases normally do not respond to "well-executed" periodontal therapy.

f) Peri-implantitis:- This is a new category established by the AAP. Patients in this category have implants that exhibit a "periodontitis-like-process" similar to natural teeth.

Fig 1: Periodontal disease affected teeth

Fig 2: Mechanism of Periodontitis induced tooth loss

1.3 In situ gel system

In situ drug delivery systems, offer an interesting potential to overcome this crucial obstacle. These are liquid preparations that can be easily injected into the periodontal pocket and then (after solvent replacement) hardened to form a gel with a custom geometry.^[18] The gel in situ remains in the form of a solution under nonphysiological conditions and forms a gel in physiological conditions under the control of stimuli such as pH, temperature, ions, and solvent present in the oral cavity.^[19,20] In situ gel provides the drug release at a controlled rate directly to the target site which reduces side effects, thus improving patient compliance.^[21] The main advantages of the implants of formation in situ are as follows: they can easily be injected into periodontal pockets, harden to form a solid implant with customized geometry, the time-controlled release of drugs, and no need to remove the empty remnants.^[22]

1.4 Advantages of in-situ oral gel^[23,24]

- ✓ Low dose is required for treatment.
- ✓ Ease of application.
- ✓ Reduced frequency of drug administration.
- ✓ Minimum local and systemic side effects.
- ✓ Increased residence time.
- ✓ It can also be administered to unconscious patient.
- ✓ Improved patient compliance and comfort.
- ✓ Improved bioavailability.

1.5 Disadvantages of in-situ oral gel

- ✓ It requires high level of fluids.
- ✓ It is more susceptible to stability problems due to chemical degradation.
- ✓ It leads to degradation due to storage problems.

1.6 Ideal characteristics of a suitable drug candidate

- ❖ It should have ability to permeate the oral mucosal tissue.
- ❖ The drug should have pleasant taste.
- ❖ The drug should have smaller and moderate molecular weight.
- ❖ It should be partially unionized at the pH of oral cavity.
- ❖ The drug should have good stability and solubility in water.

1.7 Ideal properties of polymers for in-situ oral gel

- ❖ It should have a good mouth feel property.
- ❖ The polymer should exhibit sufficient peel, shear and tensile strengths.
- ❖ It should have good shelf life.
- ❖ The polymer employed should be non-toxic, nonirritant and devoid of leachable impurities.
- ❖ It should have good wetting and spreadability property.
- ❖ It should not aid in cause secondary infections in the oral mucosa/dental region.
- ❖ It would be ideal to have a polymer that would have local enzyme inhibition action along with penetration enhancing property.
- ❖ The polymer should be readily available and should not be very expensive.

1.8 Classification of in situ gelling polymers

Based on their origin, polymers can be classified or the mechanism of gelation. According to a source in situ, gelling systems are classified into two types.^[25-29]

- a) Natural polymers (e.g., Alginate acid, carrageenan, chitosan, guar gum, gellan gum, pectin, sodium hyaluronate, xanthan gum, xyloglucan, etc.)

- b) Synthetic or semi-synthetic polymers (e.g., CAP, HPMC, MC, PAA, PLGA, poloxamers)

2. PREPARATION OF IN SITU GEL

The polymer may differ based on the development of in situ gelling systems. The polymeric solution was prepared by dispersing required quantities of polymers and copolymers in distilled water using a magnetic stirrer until the polymers completely dissolve. After the preparation of an aqueous drug solution, transferred to a primarily prepared polymeric solution with continuous stirring until to get a homogeneous solution, and then add excipients based on the delivery system. Finally, make up the volume with distilled water.^[30]

Fig.3 Thermally triggered system

The ideal critical temperature range for such system is ambient and physiologic temperature, such that clinical manipulation is facilitated and no external source of heat other than that of body is required for trigger gelation. Three main strategies exist in engineering of thermos-responsive sol-gel polymeric system. For convenience, temperature-sensitive hydrogels are classified into negatively thermosensitive, positively thermosensitive, and thermally reversible gels. Negative temperature-sensitive hydrogels have a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) and contract upon heating above the LCST. Polymers with low critical temperature (LCST) transition between ambient and physiologic temperature is used for this purpose. A positive temperature sensitive hydrogel has an upper critical solution temperature (UCST), such hydrogel contracts

3. APPROACHES OF IN SITU GELS

There are four generally defined mechanisms used for triggering the in situ gel formation of biomaterial:

- A. Physiological stimuli (e. g. temperature and pH)
- B. Physical stimuli (e. g. solvent exchange or diffusion and swelling)
- C. Chemical stimuli (e. g. enzymatic, chemical and photo-initiated polymerization)

A. Physiological stimuli

Based on physiological stimuli classified into two categories:

Temperature-induced in situ gelling systems or thermally triggered systems: Temperature-sensitive hydrogels are probably the most commonly studied. The use of biomaterial whose transitions from sol-gel is triggered by increase in temperature is an attractive way to approach in-situ formation.

upon cooling below the UCST. Polymer networks of poly(acrylic acid) (PAA) and polyacrylamide (PAAm) or poly(acrylamide-co-butyl methacrylate) have positive temperature dependence of swelling. The most commonly used thermos-reversible gels are these prepared from poly(ethylene oxide)-b-poly(propylene oxide)-b-poly(ethylene oxide). Polymer solution is a free flowing liquid at ambient temperature and gels at body temperature.^[31,32]

pH triggered systems: Another formation of in situ gel based on physiologic stimuli is formation of gel is induced by pH changes. All the pH-sensitive polymers contain pendant acidic or basic groups that either accept or release protons in response to changes in environmental pH. The polymers with a large number of ionizable groups are known as polyelectrolytes.

Fig.4 pH triggered system

Swelling of hydrogel increases as the external pH increases in the case of weakly acidic (anionic) groups, but decreases if polymer contains weakly basic (cationic) groups.^[33] Polyvinylacetal diethylaminoacetate (AEA) solutions with a low viscosity at pH 4 form hydrogel at neutral pH condition. Drug formulated in liquid solutions have several limitations, including limited bioavailability and propensity to be easily removed by salivary fluid.^[34] Mixtures of poly(methacrylic acid) (PMA) and poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) also has been used as a pH sensitive system to achieve gelation.^[35]

B. Physical stimuli: When a material absorbs water from the surrounding environment, in situ formation may also occur and expand to the desired space.

Swelling: In situ formation may also occur when material absorbs water from surrounding environment and expand to occupy desired space. One such substance is myverol 18-99 (glycerol mono-oleate), which is polar lipid that swells in water to form lyotropic liquid crystalline phase structures. It has some bioadhesive properties and can be degraded in-vivo by enzymatic action.^[36]

Solvent exchange/Diffusion: This method involves the diffusion of solvent from polymer solution into

surrounding tissue and results in precipitation or solidification of polymer matrix. N-methyl pyrrolidone (NMP) has been shown to be useful solvent for such system.^[37]

C. Chemical reactions: Chemical reactions that result in situ gelations may involve precipitation of inorganic solids by following processes.

Chemical polymerization or ionic cross-linking: Polymers may undergo phase transition in presence of various ions. Some of the polysaccharides fall into the class of ion-sensitive ones. While k-carrageenan forms rigid, brittle gels in reply of small amount of K^+ , i-carrageenan forms elastic gels mainly in the presence of Ca^{2+} . Gellan gum commercially available as Gelrite® is an anionic polysaccharide that undergoes in situ gelling in the presence of mono- and divalent cations, including Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ and Na^+ . Gelation of the low-methoxy pectins can be caused by divalent cations, especially Ca^{2+} . Likewise, alginic acid undergoes gelation in presence of divalent/polyvalent cations e. g. Ca^{2+} due to the interaction with guluronic acid block in alginate chains.^[38,39]

Fig.5 Ionic cross linking

Enzymatic polymerization or enzymatic cross-linking: In situ formation catalysed by natural enzymes has not been investigated widely but seems to have some advantages over chemical and photochemical approaches. For example, an enzymatic process operates efficiently under physiologic conditions without need for potentially harmful chemicals such as monomers and initiators. Cationic pH-sensitive polymers containing immobilized insulin and glucose oxidase can swell in response to blood glucose level releasing the entrapped insulin in a pulsatile fashion. Adjusting the amount of enzyme also provides a convenient mechanism for controlling the rate of gel formation, which allows the mixtures to be injected before gel formation.^[40]

Photo-initiated polymerization: Photopolymerisation is commonly used for in situ formation of biomaterials. A solution of monomers or reactive macromer and initiator can be injected into a tissue site and the application of electromagnetic radiation used to form gel. Acrylate or similar polymerizable functional groups are typically used as the polymerizable groups on the individual monomers and macromers because they rapidly undergo photopolymerisation in the presence of suitable photoinitiator. Typically long wavelength ultraviolet and visible wavelengths are used. Short wavelength ultraviolet is not used often because it has limited penetration of tissue and biologically harmful. A ketone, such as 2,2 dimethoxy-2-phenyl acetophenone, is often used as the initiator for ultraviolet photopolymerization, whereas camphorquinone and ethyl eosin initiators are often used in visible light systems.^[41] These systems can be designed readily to be degraded by chemical or enzymatic processes or can be designed for long term persistence in vivo. Photopolymerizable systems when introduced to the desired site via injection get photo-cured in situ with the help of fiber optic cables

and then release the drug for prolonged period of time. The photo-reactions provide rapid polymerization rates at physiological temperature. Furthermore, the systems are easily placed in complex shaped volumes leading to an implant formation.^[42]

4. TYPES OF POLYMERS USED IN IN-SITU GELLING SYSTEMS

Pectin: Pectins are a family of polysaccharides, in which the polymer backbone mainly comprises α -(1-4)-D galacturonic acid residues. Low methoxypectins readily form gels in aqueous solution in the presence of free calcium ions, which crosslink the galacturonic acid chains in a manner described by egg-box model. Although the gelation of pectin will occur in the presence of H^+ ions, a source of divalent ions, generally calcium ions is required to produce the gels that are suitable as vehicles for drug delivery. The main advantage of using pectin for these formulations is that it is water soluble, so organic solvents are not necessary in the formulation. Divalent cations present in the stomach, carry out the transition of pectin to gel state when it is administered orally.^[43,44]

Xyloglucan: Xyloglucan is a polysaccharide derived from tamarind seeds and is composed of a (1-4)- β -D-glucan backbone chain, which has (1-6)- α -D xylose branches that are partially substituted by (1-2)- β -D-galactoxylose. When xyloglucan is partially degraded by β galactosidase, the resultant product exhibits thermally reversible gelation by the lateral stacking of the rod like chains. The sol-gel transition temperature varies with the degree of galactose elimination. It forms thermally reversible gels on warming to body temperature.^[45-47]

Gellan gum: Gellan gum (commercially available as Gelrite TM or Kelcogel TM) is an anionic deacetylated exocellular polysaccharide secreted by *Pseudomonas elodea* with a tetrasaccharide repeating unit of one α -L-rhamnose, one β -D-glucuronic acid and two β -D-glucuronic acid residues. It has the tendency of gelation which is temperature dependent or cations

induced. This gelation involves the formation of double helical junction zones followed by aggregation of the double helical segments to form a three-dimensional network by complexation with cations and hydrogen bonding with water. The formulation consisted of gellan solution with calcium chloride and sodium citrate complex.^[47,48]

Alginate acid: Alginate acid is a linear block copolymer polysaccharide consisting of β -D mannuronic acid and α -L-glucuronic acid residues joined by 1,4-glycosidic linkages. The proportion of each block and the arrangement of blocks along the molecule vary depending on the algal source. Dilute aqueous solutions of alginates form firm gels on addition of di- and trivalent metal ions by a cooperative process involving consecutive glucuronic residues in the α -L-glucuronic acid blocks of the alginate chain.^[49]

Xanthan gum: Xanthan gum is a high molecular weight extra cellular polysaccharide produced by the fermentation of the gram-negative bacterium *Xanthomonas campestris*. The primary structure of this naturally produced cellulose derivative contains a cellulosic backbone (β D-glucose residues) and a trisaccharide side chain of β -D-mannose- β -D-glucuronic acid- α -D-mannose attached with alternate glucose residues of the main chain. The anionic character of this polymer is due to the presence of both glucuronic acid and pyruvic acid groups in the side chain.^[50]

Chitosan: Chitosan is a biodegradable, thermosensitive, polycationic polymer obtained by alkaline deacetylation of chitin, a natural component

of shrimp and crab shell. Chitosan is a biocompatible pH dependent cationic polymer, which remains dissolved in aqueous solutions up to a pH of 6.236. Neutralization of chitosan aqueous solution to a pH exceeding 6.2 leads to the formation of a hydrated gel like precipitate. The pH gelling cationic polysaccharides solution are transformed into thermally sensitive pH dependent gel forming aqueous solutions, without any chemical modification or cross linking by addition of polyol salts bearing a single anionic head such as glycerol, sorbitol, fructose or glucose phosphate salts to chitosan aqueous solution.^[51,52]

Carbopol: Carbopol is a well known pH dependent polymer, which stays in solution form at acidic pH but forms a low viscosity gel at alkaline pH. HPMC is used in combination with carbopol to impart the viscosity to carbopol solution, while reducing the acidity of the solution. Various water soluble polymers such as carbopol system- hydroxypropylmethylcellulose system, poly (methacrylic acid)-poly (ethylene glycol) come under the category of pH-induced in-situ precipitating polymeric systems.^[53]

5. ORAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

Gellan gum, pectin, xyloglucan, etc., are used for oral in situ gels. The pH-sensitive gels have potential use in site-specific delivery of drugs to specific regions of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), and some of the reported polymers and drugs, including the route of administration of in situ gelling systems showed in table 1.^[54,55]

Table 1: Summary of reported drug and polymers of in situ gelling systems.

Drug	Polymer used	Route of administration	Reference
Doxorubicin	Human serum albumin and tartaric acid derivative	Parenteral	[56]
Paracetamol and Ambroxol	Pectin	Oral	[57]
Pheniramine maleate and albumin FITC	Poly(methacrylic acid)	Parenteral	[58]
Recombinant human interleukin-2	Physically cross-linked dextran	Parenteral	[59]
Testosterone	Poly-lactic acid and PLGA	Parenteral	[60]
Theophylline	Gellan gum	Oral	[61]

6.EVALUATION OF ORAL IN-SITU GELLING SYSTEM

Clarity: The clarity may be determined by visual inspection under the black and white background.

pH: The pH was checked by using a calibrated digital pH meter immediately after preparation. In the case of ocular preparations, the pH preferably near to ocular pH to avoid eye irritation and enhance patient compatibility and tolerance.^[62]

Viscosity and rheology: At room (i.e., 25 °C) and body temperatures (i.e., 37±0.5 °C), observe the viscosity using Brookfield viscometer. Rheology was observed due to the thixotropic behavior of the gel. In situ gel preparations should show pseudo-plastic and Newtonian flow before and after the gelation process. Before and after gelling, it should be 5-1000 m Pas ('sol') and after 50-50,000 m Pas ('gel'), respectively. The gel formulation in situ should be well-formulated, so administration to the patient is proper, especially in ocular administration. However, these agents have the disadvantage of making blurred vision and leaving residue on the eyelids; due to high viscosity can cause difficulties in screening.^[63,64]

Texture analysis: The firmness, consistency and cohesiveness of formulation may be determined using texture analyzer which mainly indicates the syringe ability of sol so the formulation can easily administered in-vivo.^[65]

Accelerated stability studies: Formulation is replaced in amber colored vials and sealed with aluminum foil for the short term accelerated stability at 40°±20°C and 75±5% RH as per ICH state guidelines.^[65]

Spreadability: About 1 gm of gel was weighed and kept at the center of the glass plate (10 x10 cm) and another glass plate was placed over it carefully. 2 kg weight was placed at the center of the plate and care should be taken to avoid sliding of the plate. After 30 min the diameter of the gel in cm was measured.

Drug content: Take 1ml of formulation and adjust to 10ml in volumetric flask and then dilute with 10ml of

distilled water, 1ml from this solution again diluted with distilled water up to 10ml. After this take absorbance of prepared solution at a particular wavelength of the drug by using U.V visible spectroscopy.

Gel strength: This parameter may be evaluated using a rheometer. Depending on the mechanism of the gelling agent used a specified amount of gel is prepared in beaker, from the sol form. This gel containing beaker is raised at certain rate, so pushing a probe slowly through the gel. The changes in the load on the probe can be measured as a function of depth of immersion of the probe below gel surface.^[66]

Sol-gel transition temperature and gelling time: For In-Situ gel forming systems, the sol gel transition temperature and pH should be determined. Gelling time is the time required for the first detection of gelation of in-situ gelling system. Thermo-sensitive in-situ gel should be checked for in-situ gelling at body temperature.^[66]

Sterility testing: Sterility testing is carried out as per the IP 1996. Incubate the formulation for not less than 14days at 300°-350°C in the fluid thioglycolate medium to find the growth of bacteria and at 200°-250°C in soyabean casein digest medium to find the growth of fungi in formulation.

In vitro drug release studies: The drug release studies are carried out by using the plastic dialysis cell. The cell is made up of two half cells, donor compartment and a receptor compartment. Both half cells are separated with the help of cellulose membrane. The sol form of the formulation is placed in the donor compartment. The assembled cell is then shaken horizontally in an incubator. The total volume of the receptor solution can be removed at intervals and replaced with the fresh media. This receptor solution is analyzed for the drug release using analytical receptor media and placed on a shaker water bath at required temperature and oscillations rate. Samples are withdrawn periodically and analyzed.^[66]

Table 2: Summary of some of the marketed products of in situ systems

Manufacturing company	Name of the marketed product	Drugs used in the formulation	Reference
Akten	Akten™	Lidocaine hydrochloride	[67]
Alcon Laboratories Inc.	Pilopine HS	Pilocarpine hydrochloride	[68]
Spectrum Pharmaceuticals Thea	Virgan	Ganciclovir	[68]
Insite vision	Azasite	Azithromycin	[69]
Macromed	Cytoryn	Interleukin-2(IL-2)	[70]
Macromed	Regel Depot Technology	Human Growth Hormone	[71]
Merck and Co.Inc	Timoptic-XE	Timolol maleate	[72]

7.FUTURE PROSPECT

- To search for the penetration enhancers devoid of side effects
- To find the other triggering factors for the in-situ gel formation
- To target the drug in the posterior chamber through non-invasive route ^[73]

8.CONCLUSION:

The utilization of in situ gels providing various advantages over conventional dosage forms. The use of biocompatible, biodegradable, and water-soluble polymers for the in situ gel formulation can make excellent and excellent drug delivery systems. It can be stated that in order to develop broadly applicable hydrogels we must accomplish three-dimensional patterning of polymer gradients within hydrogels, both in terms of bioactive functional groups and scaffold material properties. The gelling process should occur under mild conditions for biomedical applications without damaging incorporated pharmaceuticals and cells. Therefore, cross links have been prepared in simple chemical reactions such as ionic-polymerization. The types and forms a polymeric system affect the biocompatibility of an in situ gelling system. The cross links in the gel can be chemically connected or physically associated forms. Depending on the type of the cross links; the degradation of the material will give different chemical entities as soluble degradation products. Also, porosity of the gel should be considered in selecting a specific application of the in situ gelling system. Finally, the chemicals used to induce gelation such as residual monomers, initiators, and cross linking agent should be carefully selected. Biocompatibility issues between the polymers and incorporated drugs are particularly important in the in situ gelling system. Introduction of very reactive functional groups to polymers facilitates the cross linking reactions of the polymer in the gel-forming procedure, but the functional groups may also show cross-reactivity with incorporated pharmaceuticals or cells after the gel formation as well as during as well as in situ gelation.

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